

PROFESSIONAL, SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL, ADMINISTRATIVE AND SUPPORT OF THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN ACTIVITIES

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Mihai Covaci, Brîndușa Covaci, Centre for Mountain Economy &
Zealandina Agency, United Kingdom & Australia

Abstract

The economic incentives that shape academic entrepreneurship are affected by the institutional characteristics of national university systems. These institutional characteristics do not affect the intensity of patenting and business creation activities. Rather, they explain the extent to which business activities may or may not help scientific entrepreneurs progress in their careers. Among these institutional features, the autonomy of the university, the mobility of staff and the principle of the principal investigator stand out as the most prominent.

Keywords: Romanian mountain activities; mountain statistic; professional, scientific and technical, administrative and support

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A study about the emergence of entrepreneurship as a field of research indicated that researchers in Anglo-Saxon countries have dominated the field for the past 20 years. The relatively strong impact of the Nordic and Netherlands countries is noteworthy. Using bibliographic coupling as a new bibliometric technique, five distinct clusters of knowledge from the entrepreneurial research literature were noted. The first cluster contains works focused on the cognitive aspects of entrepreneurship. A second related cluster includes works that elucidate the demographic and personality determinants of entrepreneurship. A third very homogeneous cluster consists primarily of conceptual works that study the origins, processes and impact of entrepreneurship. A fourth cluster deals with entrepreneurial financing and governance arrangements in new projects. The final and most heterogeneous cluster contains works that investigate topics ranging from networks and alliances; the strategies used by new businesses to gain a competitive advantage; to entry strategies designed to target international markets. A very strong relationship was observed between the first and the third group of works, an indicative finding of the conceptual nature of the works in both groups. The research results show the need for a more detailed analysis of the structure of knowledge in the field of entrepreneurship to identify smaller, emerging or disappearing topics in that

rapidly growing literature (<https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/30704637.pdf>).
(Meyer et al., 2014)

Technology transfer based on patents and spin-offs is largely the product of a specific institutional history, that of US research universities, where these characteristics have been prominent. Each introduction of these issues into the various European university systems requires first of all strong reflections and adjustments that take into account the institutional, organizational and environmental characteristics of academic research at national level. University entrepreneurs working in patenting, the establishment of companies (and more generally in technology transfer) come disproportionately from among scientific entrepreneurs with a brilliant scientific history, possibly oriented towards basic research. The economic agenda of these scientists focuses on the entrepreneurial efforts of the university, designed to gain reputation by building discipline, creating and managing laboratories and research teams, and the appetite for economic resources needed to achieve these goals (Franzoni, Chiara & Lissoni, Francesco (2006). Academic entrepreneurship, patents, and spin-offs: critical issues and lessons for Europe).

A study that highlighted the ways in which managers manage the social ambivalence of scientists working in new publicly managed research organizations underscores the relative importance of managers' behaviors
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and actions on scientists' entrepreneurial behaviors in addressing sociological ambivalence. for practice. Clear and explicit management strategies to encourage the pursuit of marketing opportunities and results demonstrate the agenda of top-down approaches to organizational change and results. The success of innovation and its implementation in the public sector is based on the skills of managers to obtain the necessary entrepreneurial behaviors. Due to the many and complex tensions surrounding public sector management and science, management must create, as far as possible, an organizational context that supports and supports "entrepreneurial" scientists. Through this study, practices aimed at identifying and managing these "entrepreneurial" types and stimulating less entrepreneurial types become a key consideration for the performance of entrepreneurs. By addressing the cognitive conflicts and "border work" of these scientists, the managers of these CRIs reduce the tensions and conflicts that arise around the new institutional and social structures. These answers are necessarily based on the normative acceptance of the professional scientific team and on the compensatory institutional and historical trajectories of the institutions ([https://researchbank.swinburne.edu.au/file/f81f47bd-089c-4831-b4ac-08edb612de77/1/PDF% 20% 28Published% 20version% 29.pdf](https://researchbank.swinburne.edu.au/file/f81f47bd-089c-4831-b4ac-08edb612de77/1/PDF%20%28Published%20version%29.pdf)).

The studies of Krabel et al. highlights two main results that spring from their empirical analysis (Internationalization of science and its influence on academic entrepreneurship). First of all, mobility is conducive to scientific entrepreneurship. Evidence suggests that foreign nationality and foreign education both predict the likelihood of being an entrepreneur in the face. Second, our results show that a certain subpopulation of scientists is commercially active and that entrepreneurship is most likely to occur within this subpopulation. Human capital, business experience - as inventions or the founding of companies - and perceptions that the commercialization of science is common or reputable are important factors influencing scientific entrepreneurship (Krabel, Stefan; Siegel, Donald S .; Slavtchev, Viktor (2009): The internationalization of science and its influence on academic entrepreneurship, Jena Economic Research Papers, No. 2009,026, Friedrich Schiller University Jena and Max Planck Institute of Economics, Jena <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/31781/1/59777191X.PDF>).

Statistics for Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities; administrative and support activities (figures 1 and 2) present an average of 31847.91 with a standard error of 8162.452.

Working hypothesis: the distribution of scores is considered normal and, therefore, parametric tests will be applied. The extreme values of the distribution, although they are in very small numbers, change the PSYCHO-SOCIAL VIEW JOURNAL (2/2021)

appearance of the histogram, by inducing a positive asymmetry, being still statistically important. The concentration of a large number of scores around the average produces a certain leptocurticity of the distribution, due to the related phenomena in the Romanian economy. The logarithm of the values obtained, according to the universally accepted statistical rules, allowed to balance the distribution according to the normal Gauss-Laplace curve.

Figure 1. Histogram for pentru Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities; administrative and support activities

Source: Author according to Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

At a first analysis, the distribution curve is relatively symmetrically central, and the scores around the average are very concentrated, with the appearance of leptocurticity, although the distribution is unimodal.

Figure 2. Chart of the Q-Q normal plot distribution for Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities; administrative and support activities after logarithm

Source: Author according to Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

The normal Q-Q plot test, after logarithm, shows a distribution of real scores around normal values, represented by the oblique line in the graph, which corresponds to a normal distribution.

The Q-Q detrended plot test, regarding the dispersion of empirical scores compared to normal, represented by the right with the score $z = 0$ for the mean and standard deviation 1, after logarithm, shows that they fall within a standard deviation, corresponding to a normal distribution.

By logarithm, the scores obtained were subjected to a statistical processing, after which all the factors involved in the study were taken into account, to obtain data as close as possible to the reality recorded in Romania, even if the measures taken in the economy unbalanced the distribution of scores. short period of time.

The importance of these tests is given by the need to carefully observe the influences of certain factors in the evolution of the sectors Professional, scientific and technical activities; administrative and support activities. Following the application of normality tests, after logarithmization, the null hypothesis must be rejected and the working hypothesis can be analyzed. The descriptive and inferential analysis will be done considering the distribution of scores within normal limits, according to the working hypothesis, for which the parametric tests are applied.

The central trend for this sector in the analyzed period shows that the population of mountainous Romania of the active enterprises in the studied sector increased from 2008 to 2018. In the analyzed period, the hypothesis of activity intensification was verified.

The statistics, presented above, and the histogram confirm the high agglomeration and the development trend of this sector in Romania. At the same time, statistics confirm the intensification of the growth rate of this sector. This sector could be one of the most valuable for mountain Romania.

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